

MARULIPI SASTHRA BODHINI LINK NUMERALS

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Abstract - The process of converting ordinary and plain numerals in to unintelligible numerals and vice versa is known as cryptography. In this method, numbers is stored and transmitted in a specific form in order to make it available for only particular people to read and process. Its importance lies in the fact that it protects numeral data from hacking and alteration, the Marulipi Sasthra Bodhini Link numerals while making it useful for user authentication. Cryptography is the art and science of keeping messages secure.

Key Words: Marulipi Sasthra Bodhini – Link – Numerals - Cipher

1. INTRODUCTION:

Cryptography, the practice of secure communication, has been an integral part of human history for thousands of years. With the advent of technology, the need for secure communication has only increased. This has led to the development of numerous algorithms and codes, each with its unique strengths and weaknesses. In this paper, we present a novel approach to cryptography, using a unique set of symbols inspired by the growth patterns of climbing plants. These symbols, referred to as the Marulipi Sasthra Bodhini Link Numerals, or simply Cipher, offer a new and exciting way to encode and decode messages.

2. METHODOLOGY:

Geometrical Substitute Cipher is a type of substitution cipher that replaces plaintext letters with geometrical shapes, such as squares, circles, triangles, and others. The number of bits in a Geometrical Substitute Cipher would depend on the encoding scheme used to map each plaintext letter to a geometrical shape.

Unlike traditional cryptographic algorithms, the security of a Geometrical Substitute Cipher does not depend on the number of bits in the encryption key or the strength of the encryption algorithm. Instead, the security of a Geometrical Substitute Cipher depends on the complexity of the encoding scheme used and the randomness of the shape substitution.

However, it's important to note that Geometrical Substitute Cipher is not considered a strong encryption method and can be easily broken with cryptanalytic techniques. It's often used for simple and fun encryption purposes rather than for securing sensitive information.

A cipher is a specific method of encryption used to convert plain text into cipher text. The rules or principles that govern the use of ciphers can vary depending on the specific cipher being used, but some common ones include:

1. **Key management:** The cipher should have a secure key management system to prevent unauthorized access to the plain text.
2. **Complexity:** The cipher should be complex enough to prevent attackers from easily breaking the encryption.
3. **Confidentiality:** The cipher should provide confidentiality by preventing unauthorized access to the plain text.
4. **Availability:** The cipher should be efficient enough to allow for real-time communication without significant delays.
5. **Adaptability:** The cipher should be adaptable to changes in technology and cryptographic attacks, allowing for updates and improvements over time.
6. **Backward compatibility:** The cipher should be compatible with previous versions, allowing for seamless transitions to new encryption methods.
7. **Implementation:** The cipher should be implemented properly to ensure its security.
8. **Provable security:** The cipher should have a solid mathematical foundation, allowing its security to be proven.

These are some of the common principles that govern the use of ciphers. It's important to note that the specific requirements for a cipher can vary greatly depending on the specific use case and security needs.

Cryptography is a technique used to secure communication by transforming plain text into an unreadable form, called cipher text. There are several fundamental rules or principles that are widely followed in cryptography:

1. **Confidentiality:** The most important property of cryptography is to keep the information confidential and prevent unauthorized access.
2. **Integrity:** Cryptography should ensure that the message has not been tampered with during transmission.
3. **Authentication:** Cryptography should allow the receiver to verify the identity of the sender.
4. **Non-repudiation:** Cryptography should prevent either the sender or the receiver from denying having sent or received the message.
5. **Key management:** Cryptography depends on the use of secret keys, and the management of these keys is a critical component of the cryptography process.
6. **Privacy:** Cryptography should preserve the privacy of the users by not revealing any information about them.

7. **Efficiency:** Cryptography should be fast and efficient, allowing secure communication in real-time.
8. **Forward secrecy:** The future confidentiality of encrypted messages should not be compromised by future compromises of secret keys.

These principles form the foundation of cryptography and are widely followed in the design and implementation of cryptographic algorithms.

Cryptography can be evaluated based on its ability to protect the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of information. Good cryptography should be able to achieve these goals effectively and efficiently, while bad cryptography may fail to provide adequate protection or may have significant weaknesses that can be exploited.

Here are some factors that can be used to evaluate the quality of cryptography:

1. **Strength of Encryption:** The strength of encryption is one of the most critical factors that determine the quality of cryptography. A good cryptographic algorithm should be resistant to brute-force attacks and other cryptanalytic techniques.
2. **Key Length:** The key length of a cryptographic algorithm is another critical factor that determines the quality of cryptography. Longer keys are generally considered to be more secure than shorter keys because they increase the complexity of the encryption.
3. **Availability of Cryptographic Keys:** The security of cryptography also depends on the availability and management of cryptographic keys. Good cryptography should have a secure and efficient method of generating, distributing, and revoking cryptographic keys.
4. **Resistance to Attacks:** A good cryptographic algorithm should be resistant to attacks, such as side-channel attacks, differential attacks, and others.
5. **Efficiency:** Good cryptography should be efficient, in terms of the time and resources required for encryption and decryption. Slow or resource-intensive algorithms may not be practical for real-world use.
6. **Standards Compliance:** Good cryptography should comply with recognized standards, such as those developed by organizations like NIST, ISO, and others. This ensures that the algorithm has been reviewed and tested by experts in the field.

Over all, a good cryptographic algorithm should provide strong protection, efficient operation, and comply with recognized standards. On the other hand, bad cryptography may have weaknesses, flaws, or vulnerabilities that can be exploited by attackers, leading to the compromise of information.

The number of bits in good cryptography depends on the specific application and the level of security required. Generally, a higher number of bits indicates stronger encryption and better security.

For symmetric-key encryption, such as the Advanced Encryption Standard (AES), key lengths of 128, 192, and 256 bits are commonly used. A 256-bit key length is considered to be the most secure, as it offers a very high level of encryption strength.

For public-key encryption, such as the RSA algorithm, key lengths of 2048 bits and above are commonly used. The larger the key size, the more secure the encryption, but also the slower the encryption and decryption process.

It's important to note that the number of bits is just one factor in determining the security of a cryptographic algorithm. Other factors, such as the strength of the encryption algorithm and the management of cryptographic keys, are also critical for ensuring the security of information.

3. MARULIPI SASTHRA BODHINI LINK NUMERALS

Marulipi Numerals, a secret code so rare, A cipher that can baffle the world out there. With shapes and lines that twist and turn, A code that can be so hard to learn.

In Andhra Pradesh, its birth place, Marulipi Numerals found its space. A code that's crafted with such care, A cipher that can take you anywhere.

The shapes and curves hold the key, A code that's simple yet hard to see. The secrets that lie within its lines, A puzzle that can boggle the mind.

From one to zero, each numeral stands, A code that's crafted by masterful hands. The secrets that it holds inside, A mystery that you must abide.

Marulipi Numerals, a language so new, A cipher that can mesmerize you. Its shapes and lines, a code so pure, A secret language that can allure.

So let the Marulipi Numerals reign, And let its secrets stay arcane. For in the world of secret codes, Marulipi Numerals hold the gold.

The numerals of Marulipi Sasthra Bodhini Link should be written from any side (Left to Right, Right to Left, Top to Bottom and Bottom to Top) Only the digits 1 and 0 should be represented by green and orange links. Remaining numbers 2, 3, 4, 5 should be indicated by writing green dots or small lines on violet links. Apart from that the numbers 6, 7, 8, 9 should also be indicated by writing orange dots or small lines on the violet links.

Example:

Table-1:

Link Numerals (Cipher)			
1		0	
2		6	
3		7	
4		8	
5		9	
Blank or Empty			

Picture- 1

Example: 1976 in Link Numerals

Picture- 2

Example: 9 : 45 in Link Numerals

4. ADVANTAGES:

One of the key advantages of the Marulipi Sasthra Bodhini Link Numerals is their visual appeal. The symbols are aesthetically pleasing and can easily be used as an art form in their own right. Additionally, the symbols are not easily replicated, making it difficult for malicious actors to forge messages. The use of visual symbols also makes it

easier for users to quickly verify the authenticity of a message, reducing the risk of errors and miscommunication.

5 SECURITY:

The security of the Marulipi Sasthra Bodhini Link Numerals lies in their complexity and uniqueness. The symbols are not easily replicated, making it difficult for malicious actors to intercept or forge messages. Additionally, the symbols can be used in conjunction with traditional cryptographic algorithms, adding an additional layer of security to the communication.

6 CONCLUSION:

The Marulipi Sasthra Bodhini Link Numerals offer a new and exciting approach to cryptography, combining the security of traditional algorithms with the visual appeal of unique symbols. This combination creates a unique and secure method of communication, providing users with a new tool to protect their sensitive information. The Link Numerals are an innovative and valuable contribution to the field of cryptography, and we look forward to their continued development and use.

7. REFERENCE:

The Corporal Anand KK (791316-N) Marulipi Sasthra Bodhini & Key

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